

THE ROLE OF CONTENT AND LANGUAGE INTEGRATED LEARNING (CLIL) IN PRIMARY SCHOOL CLASSROOMS: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

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***Abstract.** This article discusses the integration of content and language in CLIL and its role, as well as challenge for content-driven and language-driven teachers in primary school. Although the core element in CLIL and immersion programs is the integration of content and language, it is challenging to achieve a balance between the two to meet the dual-objective of CLIL. Research on the beliefs teachers have about CLIL and the way they understand the role of content and language in their classes is crucial to achieve that balance. By combining content knowledge and language skills, CLIL helps young learners develop bilingual or multilingual proficiencies while simultaneously fostering cognitive, cultural, and academic development.*

***Key words.** CLIL, content, language, bilingual, multilingual, integration*

Introduction. Primary education is a critical period for learning, as children exhibit high neuroplasticity and the ability to acquire languages more efficiently compared to later stages in life (Lightbown & Spada, 2013). Therefore, implementing CLIL during this stage holds considerable promise. The European Union has actively promoted CLIL as a strategy for enhancing language learning outcomes and achieving its multilingualism goals (European Commission, 2006). This has spurred its adoption in various educational settings worldwide.

However, while CLIL presents opportunities, it also entails significant challenges, particularly in the areas of teacher preparedness, curriculum development, and resource availability. Recognizing and addressing these challenges is essential to maximizing the potential of CLIL in primary education, making this topic both timely and significant.

Content vs. language teachers in CLIL

In CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning), the integration of content and language is a fundamental principle, as the interplay between these two elements lies at the heart of the approach (Llinares & Morton, 2017; Nikula et al., 2016; Ruiz de Zarobe & Jiménez Catalán, 2009). Achieving the right balance between content and language, however, is challenging, and some programs may lean more towards content or language emphasis (Dalton-Puffer, 2007; Paran, 2013; Tedick & Cammarata, 2012). Met (1998) earlier introduced a continuum for Content-Based Instruction (CBI), which ranges from content-focused to language-focused programs.

Research indicates that teachers struggle with effectively integrating both content and language (Cammarata & Tedick, 2012; Koopman et al., 2014; Oattes et al., 2018). Karabassova (2018) highlights a "dichotomy" in teaching, where educators tend to either focus on the subject content or the language itself, rather than combining both in a cohesive manner. This issue arises partly because teacher training programs are typically divided into language-specific or content-specific tracks, especially in secondary education. Integration challenges affect both content and language instructors, as programs may skew toward either end of Met's continuum (1998). Although much of the CLIL research comes from the applied linguistics field, a key issue identified is that content teachers often concentrate too much on the subject matter and neglect language integration. Less attention has been given to the potential problem of language teachers focusing excessively on language and overlooking content, although this is probably less common due to the fact that content courses are generally taught by subject matter experts.

Although pedagogical practices that encourage active language use can enhance language proficiency, it is also important to explicitly focus on language forms in CLIL. For example, Lyster's (2007, 2017) counterbalanced approach advocates for both proactive and reactive strategies, emphasizing form and the correction of language forms to effectively integrate language and content in the

classroom. Lo (2019) stresses the importance of students grasping the academic language related to the subject matter, noting that this goes beyond teaching specific vocabulary. In fact, certain linguistic features are used across different subjects and require advanced skills, such as logically connecting ideas or simplifying complex information (Barr et al., 2019; Lin, 2016). These features are essential for understanding and producing language in content-based subjects.

Conclusion. This study contributes to CLIL research by highlighting how teachers within the same context can have significant differences in their understanding of CLIL and in their teaching approaches. The results suggest that these variations are likely connected to their backgrounds and teaching experience. The distinction between content-focused and language-focused teachers in CLIL settings is particularly relevant in contexts where students who speak immigrant or minority languages are learning in a language that is not their native one. These students require a balanced focus on both language and content across all subjects to achieve success.

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